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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS) is a cross-national survey project that assesses how well young people are prepared for civic life by measuring their civic knowledge and attitudes. (Issues are like global citizenship, environmental challenges, populism, and democratic backsliding are also addressed in the latest wave.) Currently, the dataset contains results from three waves: 2009, 2016, and 2022. Geographically, it covers many European countries, including Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia in all three waves, as well as Russia in the first two. The study uses a two-stage sampling design, selecting schools and then classes within them. The data are publicly available for download, along with detailed documentation, including recommendations for statistical analysis; however, some sensitive data (e.g., students' birthdates) require submitting a separate application for access (see the review for details).

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Review of the International Civic and Citizenship Education Study by Stas Gorelik

The International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS) is a survey project managed by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement. The study examines the extent to which young people across several countries and continents are prepared to act as citizens. It does so by measuring their civic knowledge, as well as their views related to civic life. Furthermore, the project provides information on curricula, as well as teaching practices used in the schools selected for the study.

Three rounds of the study are available: 2009, 2016, and 2022. In terms of its geographical coverage, the project covers Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia in each round and Russia in 2009 and 2016. As for sampling, ICCS draws on a two-stage sampling design. Schools are first randomly selected; afterwards, one or more classes within each of the schools selected in the first stage are chosen (note that teachers are sampled alongside the students in those classes). This sampling approach ensures broad representativeness of the data, yet it also means that observations are clustered and that units do not have equal probabilities of selection. The same general design applies across the three rounds (2009, 2016, and 2022); that said, sample sizes do vary across countries and over the rounds.

In 2009 and 2016, ICCS's population included students enrolled in the eighth grade (with ninth grade covered only in those cases where the average age in eighth grade was below 13.5). The study, as noted, also covers teachers, predominantly those who teach civics-related subjects. The 2022 wave kept this general sampling design.

In terms of its key topics, ICCS measures students' civic knowledge, as well as themes such as political attitudes, civic identities, trust in social and political institutions, and participation in public activities (including in one's school). Moreover, the questionnaires are designed to generate additional information on the environments in which learning occurs, covering aspects such as teaching practices in civics, how school governance is implemented, and support for civic education (across schools).

Later cycles of the project also provide insights into themes addressing newer challenges. For instance, the 2022 round paid attention to environmental problems, global citizenship, the rise of populism, and democratic backsliding. Note, however, that all responses are self-reports and may therefore be affected by social desirability and other biases (e.g., a higher "fear factor" in more repressive political environments).

The ICCS repository provides documentation on the data and public access to the data files themselves. The datasets are available in multiple formats: SAS and SPSS for the 2009 and 2016 waves, while the 2022 release also includes data prepared for analysis in R. Importantly, publicly available user guides (provided as zipped files on the website) describe, among many other things, the structure of the datasets and offer guidance on applying weights in statistical analyses (see above on sampling).

Public-use datasets can be downloaded after agreeing to a disclaimer and a license agreement. However, a number of restricted-use files contain additional sampling and identification information (e.g., testing dates or respondents' dates of birth). Scholars seeking access to these data must submit an application describing the purpose of their study and sign a separate agreement with the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.